

MICROWAVE ASSISTED PROCESSING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOCCLAY REINFORCED EPOXY

M.V.Hosur¹, A. Menon², S. Jeelani²

¹*Department of Aerospace Science Engineering and Center for Advanced Materials, Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, AL 36088, USA*

²*Center for Advanced Materials, Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, AL 36088, USA*

SUMMARY: In the current study, investigations were carried out on the processing of SC-15 epoxy resin system reinforced with Nonomer® I.30E nanoclay using a microwave. Use of microwave drastically reduces the curing time of the resin system. While conventional room temperature curing of SC-15 takes almost 24 hours, microwave curing is complete in about 30-45 minutes. Curing of neat resin, resin reinforced with nanoclay at a loading of 2% to 6% by parts was carried out at room temperature and also by using a microwave. Room temperature cured samples were studied under two conditions: 1) with no post-curing, and 2) with post curing at 100° C for 5 hours. Samples from these three sets were characterized for glass transition temperature, decomposition temperature, viscoelastic and flexural properties through DSC, TGA, DMA and 3-point flexural tests. Nanoclay reinforced epoxy samples exhibited higher thermal and mechanical properties up to a loading of 4% beyond which the trend exhibited a reversal. Properties of microwave and thermally post cured samples were considerably higher as compared to the room temperature cured samples. Also, microwave cured samples performed at par with those subjected to thermal post curing, thus exhibiting considerable advantage of savings in terms of overall process time without any compromise on the ensuing properties.

KEY WORDS: Microwave curing, nanocomposites, thermo-mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

In order to integrate the nanoscale materials as part of larger material components, it is very essential to determine the influence of the nano-phases on the properties of the larger material systems. It is a general practice to include mineral fillers to polymers in commercial production for reasons of cost reduction and stiffness improvement [1, 2]. Most studies dealing with modification of semi-crystalline polymers with inorganic particles report embrittling effects by comparing ultimate elongation and impact strength with those of unfilled resins [3-5]. Some researchers showed enhancement of toughness in rigid particles filled polypropylene and polyethylene [6-9]. In the case of micrometer sized particulates, high filler content, typically higher than 20% by volume is generally required to bring about the above stated positive effects of the fillers. This would detrimentally affect some properties of the matrix polymers such as processability, appearance, density and aging performance. There is, therefore, a need for new materials where lower particle concentration is desired. With this regard, newly developed nanocomposites would be competitive materials. Nanoscale materials such as nanocomposites provide the opportunity to explore new behavior and functionality beyond those found in conventional materials. Polymeric nanocomposites are materials that are designed and processed from selected constituents. Extremely high

surface area is one of the most attractive characteristic of the nanoparticles because it facilitates creating a great interface in a composite. According to Reynaud et al., an interphase of 1 nm thick represents roughly 0.3% of the total volume of polymer in case of micro particle filled composites, whereas it can reach 30% of the total volume in case of nanocomposites [10]. A negligible contribution made by the interphase provides diverse possibilities of performance tailoring and is able to influence the properties of the matrices to a much greater extent under rather low non-filler loading. Chun et al. report significant improvement in the tensile performance of polypropylene composites in terms of stiffening, strengthening and toughening with a low filler content of about 0.5% [11].

In conventional thermal processing, energy is transferred to the material through convection, conduction, and radiation of heat from the surfaces of the material. In contrast, microwave energy is delivered directly to materials through molecular interaction with the electromagnetic field. In heat transfer, energy is transferred due to thermal gradients, but microwave heating is the transfer of electromagnetic energy to thermal energy and is energy conversion rather than heat transfer. This difference in the way energy is delivered can result in many potential advantages to using microwaves for processing of materials. Drastic reduction in the required cure time for microwave processing of polymers and composites was reported by Williams [12]. Since the early experimental investigations of microwave curing of composites, there have been many attempts to understand the effect of microwaves, if any, on the chemical kinetics and physical properties of microwave cured polymers.

One of the most commonly reported “microwave effects” is the acceleration of the cure kinetics of thermosetting resins. The existence of the microwave effect in thermosetting resins is quite controversial, and there have been conflicting results on this topic. Marand et al. [13], Wei et al. [14], and Jordan et al. [15] have studied the cure kinetics of epoxy resin systems. In all of these investigations, the reaction rates were enhanced and times to gelation and vitrification were reduced due to microwave heating. Marand et al. showed that the molecular structure and curing agent affect the magnitude of the acceleration in microwave heating. Research by Wei and co-workers was conducted to determine the effects of microwaves on the molecular structure, and it was shown that the molecular structure of some polymers is different when cured using microwaves as compared with conventional curing. These results are in contrast to the work of Mijovic and co-workers who have noticed either no change in the cure kinetics [16] or a retardation of the cure kinetics [17] when cured by microwaves. In their recent work, an in-situ method was used to investigate the crosslinking of several different materials and they assert that the claims of accelerated cure kinetics are unfounded. The conflicting results by different laboratories indicate the need for additional work in this area. If the application of microwaves can affect the molecular structure of the polymer, then the resulting mechanical properties may be affected. Lewis et al. [18] have focused their research on using microwaves to excite chemical reactions that are not possible with traditional processing by incorporating microwave absorbing functional groups in the polymer chain. This enhanced the heating rate and resulted in a significant increase in the reaction rate. Chen et al. [19] focused on controlling the morphological features of the polymer structure by using microwaves to control the amount of phase separation in polymer blends to design the physical properties of the polymers. In a comparison of microwave and thermal cure on the mechanical properties of epoxy resin by Singer et al. [20], it was found that the tensile strength of the microwave specimens below 80% degree of cure was significantly lower than thermally cured specimens. As the extent of cure increased, the tensile strength of the microwave specimens improved, and at 100% degree of cure the mechanical strength of the microwave cured specimens surpassed the thermally cured ones. In addition, the modulus of elasticity was slightly higher in the microwave-cured specimens. Singer and coworkers suggested that reduced strength at lower degrees of cure is a result of less molecular

entanglement of the polymer network due to alignment in the electric field. The higher reported modulus could also be due to molecular arrangement in the electric field because alignment may produce higher molecular packing with lower free volume resulting in a higher modulus. The results of this investigation are consistent with the results of Bai et al. [21]. They demonstrated both increased tensile strength and modulus for microwave cured specimens.

Though considerable work is reported on the microwave characterization of polymers, little or no work is reported on the processing of nanocomposites using microwave. Hence, in the current study, investigations were carried out to cure neat and nanophased epoxy resin system and compare their properties with conventionally cured samples with or without postcuring. Properties studied include glass transition temperature, decomposition temperature, viscoelastic and 3-point flexural behavior. For these tests DSC, TGA, DMA, and Rheometrics Minimat testing instruments were used. SC-15 epoxy system and Nonomer® I.30E nanoclay which is a surface modified montmorillonite mineral that disperses to nanoclay in epoxy resin systems at 2-6% loading by parts were used.

Fig. 1: Sonics Vibracell Ultrasonic Probe with the cooling chamber

Fig. 2: Setup for microwave curing

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Processing

The resin system used in this study was SC-15 Epoxy. SC-15 is a toughened epoxy resin system widely used in the manufacturing of advanced composites. This resin system consists of 2 parts: Part A, the epoxy and Part B, the amine based hardener. The mixing ratio was 100:30 by weight. The nanoparticle used was Nonomer® I.30E nanoclay. Different nanoclay loadings used were 2-6% by parts of the epoxy. Desired amount of Part A was weighed in a small beaker. Then the requisite amount of nanoclay by parts of epoxy was added to it. Dispersion of these nanoparticles was accomplished with the help of a “Sonic Vibracell” ultrasound probe. Ultrasonic mixing uses high energy sonic waves to force an intrinsic mixing of particles and matrix via sonic cavitations. The probe was tuned to produce acoustic waves that resonate at a frequency of $20\text{kHz} \pm 50\text{Hz}$ and amplitude of 50%. During mixing, temperature of the resin increases rapidly. To alleviate this problem, the container in which the resin is sonicated is placed in a cooling chamber maintained at 5°C . The ultrasound probe immersed in the beaker with the solution and attached to the cooling unit is shown in Figure 1. The mixture of nanoclay and epoxy were sonicated for 20 minutes. The probe was immersed in such a way that it was at least 1cm deep in the solution.

After sonication, Part B was added to the epoxy-nanoclay solution and mixed for about 4-5 minutes with a mechanical stirrer. Mechanical mixing resulted in the generation of enormous bubbles in the solution. These bubbles can lead to void formation in the cured nanocomposites, thereby reducing its strength and modulus. In order to remove these bubbles, degasification of the epoxy-nanoparticle solution was done for about 15 minutes in a vacuum desiccator connected to a rotary vane vacuum pump. After degasification, the solution was poured into a container and cured at room temperature for 24 hours. The room temperature cured samples were post cured: (1) thermally in an oven for 5 hours at 100° C. For microwave curing, the epoxy/nanoclay after degasification was poured into a microwaveable petri dish and the petri dish was in turn put in a glass beaker immersed in a vessel with water. The water helped in dissipating the excess heat that might be generated when the microwave is running. Figure 2 shows the microwave set up.

Thermal and Mechanical Characterization

Differential Scanning Calorimetry DSC tests were performed on the microwave cured samples in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen using a DSC Q1000. The temperature was ramped from 40° C to 160° C at a rate of 5° C per minute. Glass transition temperature was found out from the endothermic dips in the DSC curves.

Thermo gravimetric Analysis TGA tests were performed on the epoxy / nanocomposites in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen using a Mettler Toledo TGA. The samples were heated from 35° C to 400° C at a ramp rate of 10° C per minute. The decomposition temperature was determined by analyzing the TGA curves.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis DMA analysis was done on microwave cured epoxies and nanocomposites. The samples were subjected to a vibrational force with a frequency of 1 Hz and amplitude of 20 μ m. At the same time the temperature was ramped up from 35° C to 140° C at a rate of 5° C per minute. The storage modulus as well as glass transition temperature were obtained from the storage modulus and loss modulus curves respectively.

Flexural 3 point Bend tests Flexural analysis was performed on the samples according to ASTM D790-86 maintaining a span length-depth ratio of 16:1. The stress-strain curves were plotted. The slope of the stress-strain curve was taken as the flexural modulus and the peak value of the stress-strain curve was taken as the flexural strength.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal Analysis

Results of the glass transition temperature as measured from DSC and DMA tests as well as the decomposition temperatures from the TGA tests are tabulated as shown in Table 1. These are the average of at least three samples tested in most of the cases. Glass transition temperature, T_g was measured in the DSC tests by noting the temperature at which the slope of heat flow versus temperature curve indicated sharp change as depicted in Figure 3, which gives a representative graph containing the DSC results of 2% nanoclay reinforced epoxy cured by three methods. Glass transition temperature, T_g from the DMA tests were measured from the tan delta versus temperature plots of the samples. The temperature corresponding to the peak value of tan delta was noted as the glass transition temperature. A representative plot of tan delta versus temperature is presented in Figure 4 for the neat resin system cured at different conditions. Figure 5 represents the weight% versus temperature plot of 2% nanoclay reinforced epoxy system cured under different conditions. Decomposition temperature is

measured from the midpoint of the line joining the tangential points to the onset and end set of decomposition. From the data presented in Table 1, it is clear that the addition of nanoparticles improved the T_g values by about 10°C from both DSC and DMA results. Generally, DMA results indicate a higher bound whereas DSC results indicate lower bound of T_g . Of all the samples, TPC samples had higher T_g followed by microwave cures samples and room temperature cured samples. It is only expected that TPC samples will have better crosslinking as the curing was carried out completely according to the manufacturer's specification. Our aim was to achieve properties with microwave curing that are at the most close to those exhibited by the conventional TPC. The microwave setting used in the current study can further be optimized to bring the values much closer to those exhibited by TPC. Room temperature cured samples exhibit lowest thermal properties as the polymerization is not complete and the cross linking is weaker. Decomposition temperature values showed significant increase as compared to the neat resin samples. There was an increase of $25\text{-}30^\circ\text{C}$ in decomposition temperature. There was a difference of about 10°C within the different % loadings. Optimum loading seems to be about 4%.

Fig. 3: DSC results of 2% nanoclay reinforced samples cured under different conditions

Table 1: Average thermal properties of samples cured under different conditions

Sample	Glass Transition Temperature, T_g °C						Decomposition Temperature °C		
	DSC			DMA			TGA		
	RT	MW	TPC	RT	MW	TPC	RT	MW	TPC
Neat	51	62	82	71	79	98	330	334	344
2%	49	66	87	63	98	110	355	363	370
3%	44	65	78	73	74	84	364	366	367
4%	51	71	75	73	96	101	355	356	353
5%	60	71	76	74	84	93	355	355	357
6%	58	64	72	82	87	89	361	367	362

Note: RT-room temperature, MW-microwave, TPC-thermal post cure

Fig. 4: Tan delta versus temperature plots of neat resin samples cured under different conditions

Fig. 5: Weight % versus temperature plots of neat resin samples cured under different conditions obtained from TGA tests

Table 2: Average storage modulus values of samples cured under different conditions

Sample	Storage Modulus, MPa		
	RT	MW	TPC
Neat	668	1141	1136
2%	1444	1719	1693
3%	1423	1821	1737
4%	1107	1844	1406
5%	1530	2095	1640
6%	1598	1798	1637

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Table 2 presents the data of storage modulus of samples determined from DMA tests for different nanoclay loading and different cure conditions. A representative plot of storage

modulus versus temperature is depicted in Figure 6 for neat resin system cured under different conditions. In all cases, the storage modulus of the nanoclay reinforced epoxy systems exhibited considerable increase. It is about 53% for TPC samples, 84% for MW samples and 240% for room temperature cured samples. Highest value was obtained for 3%, 5% and 6% loading in case of TPC, MW and RT cured samples respectively. At any given percentage of nanoclay loading MW cured samples exhibited highest values.

Fig. 6: Storage modulus versus temperature plots of neat resin samples

Flexural Analysis

Three point flexural analyses were carried out on 5 samples each according to ASTM D 790-86 and an average was taken. The flexural strength, strain to failure, and flexural modulus values were determined from stress-strain curves and are presented in Table 3. Figure 7 depicts a representative flexural stress-strain plot of 2% nanoclay reinforced epoxy system cured under different conditions.

Table 3: Flexural properties of neat and nanoclay reinforced epoxy samples

Sample	Flexural Strength, MPa			Strain to Failure %			Flexural Modulus, GPa		
	RT	MW	TPC	RT	MW	TPC	RT	MW	TPC
Neat	66	80	83	2.9	3.9	3.6	3.4	3.2	3.3
2%	116	146	125	3.4	5.1	3.0	4.3	5.0	4.8
3%	97	143	124	3.2	3.8	4.0	3.8	5.0	4.1
4%	90	147	143	3.1	4.0	3.6	3.5	4.5	4.5
5%	85	132	112	2.6	3.8	3.7	4.1	4.6	4.1
6%	91	125	104	2.3	4.3	2.2	4.6	4.2	2.9

Fig. 7: Flexural stress strain plots of 2% nanoclay reinforced epoxy system

From these results it is seen that the addition on nanoclay increases the flexural properties considerably. For example, in the case of neat resin samples the increase is about 30-75% in flexural strength and about 7-17% in the failure strain up to a loading of 4% and 3-35% in the flexural modulus. However, beyond 4% loading, the samples tend to become brittle and hence the failure strain is lower than that of neat resin counterpart. On the other hand, the increase in MW cured samples is 56-83% in flexural strength, 3-31% in strain to failure and 31-56% in flexural modulus. Again at loading of 3% and 5%, the failure strain was lower than that exhibited by the neat resin sample. For TPC samples, the increase was 25-72% in flexural strength, 3-11% in strain to failure and 24-45% in flexural modulus. Though the strength was higher at 6% loading, strain to failure and flexural modulus were considerably lower as compared to neat resin samples. From these studies, it can be concluded that the optimum loading percentage is about 4%. Any further increase in loading percentage makes the composite brittle. Also, it is difficult to disperse higher percentage of nanoclay which could lead to agglomeration resulting in a weaker composite.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the main focus was to optimize a method to cure the epoxy and nanocomposites directly using microwaves without any compromise on the resulting properties. A microwave setting of 45 minutes at 20% power was optimized for the neat system. While for the nano-infused system, a setting of 35 minutes at 20% power was required. The microwave processed nanocomposites exhibited improved mechanical properties over the thermal post cured and room temperature cured composites. On the other hand, the glass transition temperatures of the microwave cured samples were prominently above the room temperature cured ones and closer to the thermal post cured samples. Thus microwave curing not only reduced the processing time, but also improved the mechanical as well as the thermal properties. Overall, nanoclay loading up to 4% seems to be optimum.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support through research grants by Army Research Office (Grant No: DAAD19-01-1-0815) and National Science Foundation (Grant No: HRD-0317741) for this work.

REFERENCES

1. Rothan R.N., "Mineral Fillers in Thermoplastics, Filler Mechanisms and Characterization," *Advanced Polymer Science*, 139, 1999, pp. 67-107.
2. Pukanszky B., "Particulate Filled Polypropylene Composites," In, Karger-Kozsis J, editor. *Polypropylene, an A-Z reference*, Kluwer Academic, 1999, pp. 574-580.
3. Jancar J., Dibenedetto A. T., Dianselmo A., "Effect of Adhesion on the Fracture Toughness of Calcium Carbonate Filled Polypropylene," *Polymer Engineering Science* 33, 1993, pp. 559-563.
4. Tjong S. C., Li R. K. Y., Cheung T., "Mechanical Behavior of CaCO₃ Particle Filled β -Crystalline Phase Polypropylene Composites," *Polymer Engineering Science*, 36, 1997, pp. 166-177.
5. Dubnikova I. L., Oshmyan V. G., Gorenberg A. Y., "Mechanisms of Particulate Filled Polypropylene Finite Plastic Deformation and Fracture," *Journal of Material Science*, 32, 1997, pp. 1613-1622.
6. Premphet K., Horanont P., "Phase Structure of Ternary Polypropylene/Elastomer/Filler Composites, Effects of Elastomer Polarity," *Polymer*, 41, 2000, pp. 9283-9290.
7. Kolarik J., Jancar J., "Ternary Composites of Polypropylene/Elastomer/Calcium Carbonate, Effect of Functionalized Components on Phase Structure and Mechanical Properties," *Polymer*, 33, 1992, pp. 4961-4967.
8. Bartczak Z., Argon A. S., Cohen R. E., Weinberg M., "Toughness Mechanism in Semi Crystalline Polymer Blends, II. High Density Polyethylene Toughened with Calcium Carbonate Filler Particles," *Polymer*, 40, 1999, pp. 2347-2365.
9. Walter R., Friedrich K., Privalko V., Savadori A., "On Modulus and Fracture Toughness of Rigid Particulate Filled High Density Polyethylene", *Journal of Adhesion*, 64, 1997, pp. 87-109.
10. Reynaud E., Gauthier C. Perez J., "Nanophases in Polymers," *Review Metallurgie*, 96, No. 2, 1999, pp. 169-176.
11. Chun L. W., Ming Q. Z., Min Z. R., Klaus F., "Tensile Performance Improvement of Low Nanoparticles Filled-Polypropylene Composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, 62, 2002, pp. 1327-1340.
12. William, N. H., "Curing of epoxy resin impregnated pipe at 2450 MHz," *Journal of Microwave Power and Electromagnetic Energy*, 2, 1967, pp. 123-127.
13. Marand, E., H. R. Baker, J. D. Graybeal, "Comparison of reaction mechanisms of epoxy resins undergoing thermal and microwave cure from insitu measurements of microwave dielectric properties and infrared spectroscopy," *Macromolecules*, 25, 1992, pp. 2243-2252.
14. Wei, J., M. C. Hawley, and J. D. Delong, "Comparison of microwave and thermal cure of epoxy resins," *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 33, No. 17, 1993, pp. 1132-1140.
15. Jordan, C., J. Galy, and J. P. Pascault, "Comparison of microwave and thermal cure of an epoxy/amine matrix," *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 35, No. 3, 1995, pp. 233-239.
16. Mijovic, J., W.V. Corso, L. Nicolais, and G. d'Ambrosio, "In-situ real-time study of crosslinking kinetics in thermal and microwave fields," *Polymers for Advanced Technologies*, 9, No. 4, 1998, pp. 231-243.
17. Mijovic, J., and J. Wijaya, "Comparative calorimetric study of epoxy cure by microwave vs. thermal energy," *Macromolecules*, 23, No. 15, 1990, pp. 3671-3674.
18. Lewis, D. A., J. D. Summers, T. C. Ward, and J. E. McGrath, "Accelerated imidization reactions using microwave radiation," *Journal of Polymer Science Part A*, 30, No. 8, 1992, pp. 1647-1653.

19. Chen, M., J. W. Hellgeth, T. C. Ward, and J. E. McGrath, "Microwave processing of two phase systems, composites and polymer blends," *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 35, No. 2, 1995, pp. 144-150.
20. Singer, S. M., J. Jow, J. D. DeLong, and M. C. Hawley, "Effects of processing on tensile properties of an epoxy/amine matrix, continuous electromagnetic and/or thermal curing," *SAMPE Quarterly*, 20, No. 2, 1989, pp.14-18.
21. Bai, S. L., V. Djafari, M. Andreani, and D. Francois, "A comparative study of the mechanical behavior of an epoxy resin cured by microwaves with one cured thermally," *European Polymer Journal*, 31, No. 9, 1995, pp. 875-884.